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1 **RAPTOR-UAV: Real-Time Particle Tracking in Rivers using an Unmanned**
2 **Aerial Vehicle**

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4 Philipp Thumser and Christian Haas, I AM HYDRO GmbH - Investigation and
5 Monitoring of Hydrosystems¹, Märtishofweg 2, 78112 St. Georgen, Germany, Phone:
6 +4977249350124, Fax: +497724940820, email: philipp.thumser@iamhydro.com

7
8 Jeffrey A. Tuhtan, Juan Francisco Fuentes-Pérez and Gert Toming, Centre for
9 Biorobotics², Tallinn University of Technology, Akadeemia tee 15A-111, 12618
10 Tallinn, Estonia

11 Abstract

12 River system measurement and mapping using UAVs is both lean and agile, with the
13 added advantage of increased safety for the surveying crew. A common parameter of
14 fluvial geomorphological studies is the flow velocity, which is a major driver of
15 sediment behavior. Advances in fluid mechanics now include metrics describing the
16 presence and interaction of coherent structures within a flow field and along its
17 boundaries. These metrics have proven to be useful in studying the complex
18 turbulent flows but require time-resolved flow field data, which is normally unavailable
19 in geomorphological studies. Contactless UAV-based velocity measurement provides
20 a new source of velocity field data for measurements of extreme hydrological events
21 at a safe distance, and could allow for measurements of inaccessible areas. Recent
22 works have successfully applied large-scale particle image velocimetry (LSPIV) using
23 UAVs in rivers, focusing predominantly on surficial flow estimation by tracking
24 intensity differences between georeferenced images. The objective of this work is to
25 introduce a methodology for UAV based real-time particle tracking in rivers
26 (RAPTOR) in a case study along a short test reach of the Brigach River in the
27 German Black Forest. This methodology allows for large scale particle tracking
28 velocimetry (LSPTV) using a combination of floating, infrared light-emitting particles
29 and a programmable embedded color vision sensor in order to simultaneously detect
30 and track the positions of objects. The main advantage of this approach is its ability
31 to rapidly collect and process the position data, which can be done in real-time. The
32 disadvantages are that the method requires the use of specialized light-emitting
33 particles, which in some cases cannot be retrieved from the investigation area, and
34 that the method returns velocity data in unscaled units of px/s. This work introduces
35 the RAPTOR system with its hardware, data processing workflow, and provides an
36 example of unscaled velocity field estimation using the proposed method. First

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3 37 experiences with the method show that the tracking rate of 50 Hz allows for position
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5 38 estimation with sub-pixel accuracy, even considering UAV self-motion. A comparison
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7 39 of the unscaled tracks after Savitzky-Golay filtering shows that although the time-
8
9 40 averaged velocities remain virtually the same, the filter reduces the standard
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11 41 deviation by more than 40% and the maxima by 20%.

12 13 14 15 16 42 **Keywords**

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19 43 UAV, LSPIV, PIV, Drone, velocimetry, river, particle tracking

20 21 22 23 44 **Introduction**

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25
26 45 Geomorphological change occurs across a wide spectrum of spatiotemporal scales,
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28 46 and thus modelling and measurement efforts to capture its dynamics require a
29
30 47 diverse pallet of tools. Turbulent fluid flows are ubiquitous in both marine and
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32 48 freshwater environments, and are most commonly analyzed after being broken down
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34 49 via Reynolds averaging into the time-average and fluctuating components.
35
36 50 Fundamentally, there can be large differences in the spatial and temporal distribution
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38 51 of instantaneous flow fields from the time-averaged velocities most commonly
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40 52 applied in field studies (Magirl et al., 2009). However, recent advances in fluid
41
42 53 mechanics now allow for the study of turbulence structure. Fundamentally, this
43
44 54 entails the education and tracking of large vortices (commonly referred to as
45
46 55 “eddies”), which form coherent structures within the flow, and at fluid-solid
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48 56 boundaries (Tanaka and Kida, 1993). Indeed, the geomorphology community has
49
50 57 recognized the presence and potential impacts of coherent structures in shallow
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52 58 marine flows (Zimmermann, 1981), as well as their role in river channel confluences
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54 59 (Lane et al., 2000). Coherent structures can form material lines (Haller, 2015), which
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3 60 physically segregate the mass flux of water and sediment into distinct regions of the
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5 61 river, and can have significant impacts on sediment transport, especially downstream
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7 62 of instream structures (Kirkil and Constantinescu, 2009).
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9
10 63 The inclusion of coherent structures would thus allow for a more detailed and
11
12 64 physically rigorous interrogation of the dynamics involved in the flows driving
13
14 65 geomorphological change. This is critical for studies of morphodynamic processes
15
16 66 such as scour near in-stream structures. The interaction between coherent structures
17
18 67 and suspended sediments have also been found to influence transport dynamics in
19
20 68 both clear and sediment laden flows (Cellino and Lemmin, 2004). Thus the inclusion
21
22 69 of coherent structures in fluvial geomorphological studies has shown that they can
23
24 70 provide deeper insight into local flow and sediment interactions. However, the
25
26 71 identification and tracking of coherent flow structures most often requires time-
27
28 72 resolved as opposed to time-averaged flow fields. Thus in order to include the study
29
30 73 of coherent structures and their geomorphological significance, it is first necessary to
31
32 74 develop new flow measurement techniques capable of providing time-resolved flow
33
34 75 field data. Currently, the most promising technologies developed capable of
35
36 76 delivering such data are particle imagery based methods.
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39
40 77 Particle image velocimetry (PIV) and particle tracking velocimetry (PTV) are common
41
42 78 velocity measurement techniques used in fluid mechanics. They are both image
43
44 79 based, non-intrusive, whole-field measurement systems. Fundamentally, both
45
46 80 methods consist of the same components: an imaging device (typically a high speed
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48 81 CCD camera), a light source (pulsed or continuous laser) with light sheet optics,
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50 82 tracers particles and a PC to control the camera and run the image processing
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52 83 software (Raffel et al., 2007).
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56 84 PIV data processing utilizes pattern matching algorithms on images with high particle
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58 85 concentration. Images are divided into small interrogation windows and the
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86 movement of particle images is detected typically using cross-correlation of filtered
87 pixel intensities (Adrian, 1991). The result is a field of Eulerian velocity vectors on a
88 regular grid whose extent and resolution are defined by user-defined interrogation
89 windows. PTV uses lower particle concentration and velocities are calculated by
90 tracking the movement of individual particles giving Lagrangian velocity vectors as
91 output (Adamczyk and Rimai, 1988; Tapia et al., 2006). Setting up a PIV
92 measurement system in lab conditions is expensive and can be technically
93 challenging, however if done correctly measurement errors of 1% or less are
94 achieved (Keane and Adrian, 1990; Westerweel, 1997).

95 Although the majority of applications are under laboratory settings, both of these
96 methods are gaining field applications in rivers. Compared to conventional river flow
97 measurement techniques, PIV/PTV can provide whole-field measurements, are non-
98 intrusive, can be used to measure shallow waters, and measurements can be
99 performed remotely, e.g. from the shore, a bridge spanning the river or UAV. Since
100 the spatial extent of the measured region differs significantly in field applications from
101 those in the lab, the terms “large scale” PIV (LSPIV) and large scale PTV (LSPTV)
102 are used to differentiate them from laboratory-scale applications (Fujita et al., 1998).
103 When comparing these methods to regular PIV/PTV, generally the large scale
104 technologies are cheaper, more robust but less accurate, as regular video or photo
105 cameras and natural lightning conditions are used. Requirements on the tracer
106 particles must also be relaxed as particles moving along the water surface instead of
107 on a thin layer below the surface (e.g. laser sheet in lab settings) must be used for
108 tracking. Often natural particles e.g. foam, pieces of ice or vegetation, etc. are
109 present and can be sufficient for tracking. If artificial particles are needed their size,
110 density and shape have to be selected carefully to achieve the desired measurement

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3 111 accuracy and to avoid the formation of conglomerates, which can lead to spurious
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5 112 surficial velocity estimates (Tang et al., 2008).
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7 113 In many outdoor applications, the camera must be installed at an oblique angle
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9 114 between the camera and the flow field, resulting geometrical and lens distortions
10
11 115 (Creutin et al., 2003; Fujita et al., 1998). These distortions must be removed before
12
13 116 processing the recorded images. Other parameters that could alter measurements
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15 117 are wind, waves, non-uniform seeding and reflection from the water surface. Kim has
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17 118 identified 27 error sources that affect the measurements and determined te average
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19 119 velocity measurement error to be about 10% (Kim, 2006), this result also agrees with
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21 120 the error when comparing LSPIV and ADCP (acoustic Doppler current profiler)
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23 121 profiler measurements (Le Coz et al., 2010), while it seems to slightly over-predicted
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25 122 the mean flow velocities but still ate representative of the flow (Legout et al., 2012). In
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27 123 laboratory conditions, the average measurement errors of 3.5% and as low as 1.0%
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29 124 have been reported (Li et al., 2013). Legout indicates that LSPIV could be used to
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31 125 obtain surface velocity measurements with a relatively low sensitivity to parameter
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33 126 changes in the range +/-50% around 'ideal' values based on expert knowledge about
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35 127 the image processing step (Legout et al., 2012).
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40 128 Recently UAVs mounted with automated gimbals have been used to set the camera
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42 129 in desired positions while keeping it perpendicular to the flow field, resulting a
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44 130 difference of only 1.35% between the flow discharge measurements with LSPIV and
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46 131 ADCP (Patalano et al., 2015).
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49 132 LSPIV/LSPTV has been successfully implemented for measuring the flow speed and
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51 133 profile (both real-time and offline data analysis) in rivers during regular conditions,
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53 134 during floods and even near hydraulic structures (Hauet et al., 2008; Muste et al.,
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55 135 2008) and in storm water retention ponds (Gillis et al., 2015). Interesting field studies
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57 136 applied LSPIV with non conventional methods in field studies in rivers (Barker et al.,
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3 137 2010) and even estimation of discharge was already applied in a field study
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5 138 (Gunawan et al., 2012), but both with very high efforts.

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7 139 Typical LSPTV data processing workflow starts with image orthorectification and
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9 140 removing distortions caused by lens. This is followed by standard PIV/PTV
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11 141 procedures: image preprocessing to emphasize the seeding particles; detecting
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13 142 single particles (or in case of LSPTV pattern matching); matching pixels to real world
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15 143 coordinates in m or cm; post processing the data – typically correcting spurious
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17 144 vectors, interpolating the missing vectors and finally smoothing the data (Fujita et al.,
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19 145 1998; Nogueira et al., 1997; Raffel et al., 2007).

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22 146 First field studies have already proved the applicability of UAV mounted particle
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24 147 tracking methods at smaller scales and low heights (Pagano et al., 2014; Tauro et al.,
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26 148 2015). The field studies applying LSPIV to UAVs use either artificial tracers (i.e. small
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28 149 wooden pieces, oranges) (Patalano et al., 2015) or natural tracers floating on the
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30 150 water (Fujita et al., 2015). Despite a strong limitation to the UAV flying height, due to
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32 151 particle recognition, merging LSPIV and UAV provides encouraging first results, and
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34 152 the integration of UAV technology and optical measurements is expected to be highly
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36 153 beneficial for experimental studies (Tauro, 2015).

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39 154 The one major drawback of using optical methods is the required processing
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41 155 associated with the velocity estimation. In this work, we introduce a methodology
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43 156 which uses hardware commonly used in terrestrial robotics for real-time object
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45 157 tracking. The system is able to detect and follow light-emitting tracer particles, saving
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47 158 the pixel positions relative to a fixed reference target. Thus a substantial part of the
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49 159 object recognition and tracking data processing workflow can be automated using
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51 160 commodity hardware.
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161 Study Site

162 The river Brigach in the Black Forest in Germany is one of two main headwater
163 streams of the Danube River. With a total length of 40.2 km (LUBW, 2014), a total
164 basin area of 196.69 km² (LUBW, 2016) and a mean annual flow rate of 3.21 m³/s at
165 the confluence with river Breg the second tributary (LUBW, 2015). The region of
166 interest (ROI) at the study site is a small section (6 x 10 m) on the Brigach river
167 (48°4'36.55" N, 8°24'37.00" E), and is show in Figure 1.

168 A series of ground control points (GCP) were placed to provide spatial referencing,
169 as shown in Figure 1, consisting of white PVC tiles with an area of 0.50 x 0.50 m, and
170 a 4.0 cm width black marking cross and number. Each GCP was placed along the left
171 riverbank at a distance of 1.0 m between each GCP. The reference target used to
172 correct the UAV drift during real-time tracking was placed on the right riverbank in
173 direction of flow.

174 The field location was primarily chosen as it represents a common size and
175 morphological condition of many small German rivers, and secondly for its easy
176 accessibility and suitability for UAV imagery collection (e.g. not close to a roadway
177 and with no overhanging vegetation or power lines). The water depth within the ROI
178 during the case study ranged between 0.1 m and 0.5 m, with some small boulders (>
179 50 cm in mean diameter) protruding from the water surface. Thus the selected
180 location can be considered to be a realistic case study.

181 Materials and Methods

182 Hardware

183 Real-time particle tracking was performed using a CMUcam5 (Figure 2(a)), which is
184 outfitted with an Omnivision OV9715 ¼" image sensor with an input resolution of

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3 185 1280 x 800 px (16:10 aspect ratio), a M12 lens (field of view: 75° horizontal, 47°
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5 186 vertical), and onboard NXP LPC4330 processor (204 MHz, dual core). The camera
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7 187 module was modified to detect infrared (IR) light. The CMUcam5 is designed for
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9 188 indoor and outdoor use, and is capable of tracking a maximum of 6000 objects per
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11 189 second, or 135 detected objects per frame. It can be configured to recognize dual
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13 190 color codes for discreet object recognition as well. During the case study, the data
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15 191 were output at the maximum processing speed of 50 Hz (50 fps) at 640 x 400 px.
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17 192 The processing speed has two major impacts on the accuracy of the PTV velocity
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19 193 estimate; (i) the tracked positions can be smoothed in time with reduced impact on
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21 194 the ability of the method to record local flow accelerations. At 50 Hz there are
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23 195 multiple estimates of the particle position with little or no motion occurring between,
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25 196 smoothing thus provides a stable “mean” estimate for each location, and (ii) at 50 Hz
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27 197 and a flight height of < 50 m, the camera resolution allows for velocity field estimates
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29 198 at a resolution $\leq 1 \text{ m}^2$. Thus considering the practical applications and limitations of
30
31 199 the proposed method, it is necessary to use the maximum processing speed to
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33 200 ensure uniform spatiotemporal accuracy of the surficial velocity field. Note that the
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35 201 device has a higher input than output resolution. Data were read out as ASCII text file
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37 202 via serial connection (9600 baud) using the Arduino Duemilanove physical-
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39 203 computing-platform. The exported information included the CMUCam5’s unique
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41 204 object identifier (“block number”), the x and y camera sensor position, and the width
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43 205 and height of a rectangular region encompassing each detected object.
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45 206 The IR targets used in this work consisted of a single 360° IR-LOCK tracking pod,
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47 207 powered using a 180 mAh 3 cell 11.1 V Lipoly battery (Turnigy nano-tech 3S 25)
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49 208 floating on a 30 cm diameter styrofoam disk.
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51 209 A custom made hexacopter was used for carrying the tracking equipment (Figure
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53 210 2(b)). The copter has a maximum payload of around 2.5 kg. The overall hardware
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3 211 solution including copter and all measuring equipment weights approximately 4.8 kg,
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5 212 which importantly remains within the German regulation for UAVs maintain < 5.0 kg
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7 213 total weight. 6 brushless motors with a total available maximum power of 4.5 kW
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9 214 drive the copter, while a DJI NAZA-M V2 Multirotor Autopilot controls the position
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11 215 during the flight with an added d-GPS for position correction and air pressure sensor
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13 216 for height. Flight telemetry is transmitted by radio signal to a ground station (DJI iPad
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15 217 Ground Station), which is connected to a tablet computer displaying the flight
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17 218 parameters visible to the pilot.
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20 21 219 **Data collection**

22
23 220 Before takeoff, the maximum possible working distance between IR target and
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25 221 sensor was determined for actual on-site light conditions. The target was moved in
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27 222 1m-steps apart from the sensor (z-axis) and then moved in the same distance in x
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29 223 and y.
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32 224 The UAV was launched and controlled manually by the operator into a fixed position
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34 225 in the center of the ROI. The flying height above ground was adjusted to 15m above
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36 226 ground level, according the maximum distance between IR sensor and emitter, which
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38 227 were determined shortly before on the actual light conditions. The UAV was oriented
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40 228 facing its front and the camera at a riverbank, due to the 16:10 aspect ratio of the
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42 229 camera. This ensured that with this specific hardware and at an altitude of 15m
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44 230 above ground, the tracking module was able to track an area or approximately 25 m²
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46 231 (in direction of the river) x 15 m. The coverage of this area was tested with several
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48 232 flights before and confirmed. After bringing the UAV in position the IR target was
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50 233 released on the water surface upstream of the ROI, to ensure an appropriate start-up
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52 234 length in advance. After passing the ROI, the target was picked up and released
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54 235 again upstream of the ROI. The procedure was repeated several times and different
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56 236 flights were conducted. Influences of wind during the whole test were negligible.
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237 **Data Post-Processing**

238 The CMUCam5 records the real-time tracking information to a text file, which
239 provides the raw data. Initially, this data represents a running collection of block
240 number coordinates defined by their spatial coordinates and time stamps which must
241 be filtered to obtain the real position and track of the particles (Figure 3).

242 One difficulty of using the raw data input is that the tracking system reports block
243 numbers at each recorded detection event, in order of the size of the object's
244 detection region. The size of this region is influenced by a multitude of factors,
245 including the inclination of the target with respect to the camera, the intensity of the
246 target emitter, and most importantly the ambient lighting. Currently, it is not feasible
247 to overcome these factors using hardware modifications, as naturally occurring
248 variations in field conditions (most notably the lighting) cannot be overcome. The first
249 step of the data processing workflow is thus to reorganize the distribution of tracked
250 objects using the raw data as input (Figure 4(a)), where each object position is
251 classified (Figure 4(b)). Each object corresponds to a single detection event
252 separated in time. Here we defined particle objects as belonging to the same class
253 when they are within a threshold of space and time, considering always that points
254 with same time stamps belong to different classes. This condition is set due to the
255 physical impossibility of any one object being tracked at two different locations at the
256 same time. The Euclidian distance, d is applied to measure the distance between two
257 objects a and b at two different pixel-wise locations a_i and b_i (Equation 1). The
258 thresholds were set depending on the experimental arrangement used (e.g. for the
259 arrangement defined in this work, $d_{space} = 20$ px and $d_{time} = 2000$ ms). Likewise, in
260 cases of point superposition, additional considerations can be made (e.g. trajectory
261 tracking considering previous position of the targets).

$$d(a, b) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (a_i - b_i)^2} \quad (1)$$

263 Due to the capability of the hardware for simultaneous tracking of multiple particles, it
 264 becomes the case that different particles will have the same time stamp. Indeed, in
 265 our experiment a static reference target GCP was registered together with the mobile
 266 target positions in order to correct the lateral UAV movement at each time step. In
 267 the second step of the data processing workflow, the reference target class data is
 268 used to correct the position of the remaining class (Figure 4(c)).

269 First, the fixed, global location of the reference target is assigned fixed, global pixel
 270 coordinates. In this study, we chose $x_{ref} = 200$ and $y_{ref} = 200$ px as it corresponded
 271 closely to the average location of the target for all images. Next, the pixel-wise
 272 location of the target is determined for the individual images as x_{GCP} , y_{GCP} . Finally,
 273 for each image, the raw coordinates of a given pixel $x_{i,raw}$, $y_{i,raw}$ are corrected to the
 274 global reference location x_i , y_i using the offset correction provided by Equation 2.
 275 Results of the offset are depicted graphically in Figure 4(c). Additional
 276 considerations such as interpolating between the raw coordinates and ground control
 277 can be applied in cases when a perfect match (identical time stamp) is not
 278 encountered.

$$\begin{aligned} x_i &= x_{i,raw} + (x_{ref} - x_{GCP}) \\ y_i &= y_{i,raw} + (y_{ref} - y_{GCP}) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

280 It was found (Table 1) that the mean deviations during the observation of a single
 281 track between the target reference and its true fixed location, $(\mu_{\Delta x}, \mu_{\Delta y})$ was
 282 consistently less than or equal to $1/10^{\text{th}}$ of a pixel displacement, and the standard
 283 deviation in both the lateral and streamwise directions, $(\sigma_{\Delta x}, \sigma_{\Delta y})$ were also less than 1
 284 pixel for all observations. This despite less than ideal conditions in which light rain

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3 285 and wind were occurring, shows that the 50 Hz detection rate aids in keeping the
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5 286 overall position error, even including UAV self-motion, down to a manageable level.
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7 287 The third step is to filter the classified and corrected spurious object motion recorded
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9 288 when the target detection does not correspond to motion caused by the target
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11 289 floating down the river, e.g. when the target is held ready for release (Figure 4(d)).
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13 290 Since the particles will be tracked once they are detected by CMUCam5 sensor, all
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15 291 detections not corresponding to tracks when the device is on the water surface must
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17 292 be automatically eliminated. Considering the case study data, this was easily
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19 293 achieved by considering the main direction vector of the river and comparing nearby
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21 294 points within the same class. The final step in the workflow is to combine multiple
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23 295 corrected and filtered datasets (data fusion) to obtain a map of all the tracks within
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25 296 the ROI (Figure 4(e)).
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30 297 **Particle Smoothing**

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32 298 After the individual tracks from multiple flights have been post-processed, the
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34 299 resulting data set can be used to estimate the surficial velocities. In this work, the
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36 300 velocity analysis was performed in px/s as our objective was to field test the
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38 301 prototype and develop data processing workflows, which can then be applied in a
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40 302 larger and more complicated field study including the spatial comparison of
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42 303 measured and estimated surficial velocities. Here we have chosen to apply the
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44 304 Savitzky-Golay filter (Figure 5), which is commonly applied to both PIV and PTV
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46 305 derived datasets (Kolaas et al., 2015). The moving window size used for the filter
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48 306 was set to 10 observations, and the piecewise approximation was performed using a
49
50 307 2nd order polynomial fit (Savitzky and Golay, 1964).
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52 308 The filter is needed for two reasons: first, the spatial positions even after post-
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54 309 processing can contain gaps due to failed detections at each recording interval
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56 310 (maximum is 50 Hz). The second reason is that after spatial smoothing has been
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3 311 performed, temporal smoothing is also required, especially in cases where the
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5 312 particle comes to a halt (e.g. stuck on a rock or other in-stream obstruction), and
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7 313 where sudden motion occurs upon the tracer particle becoming free.
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10 11 314 Results

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14 315 First flight tests with the copter show deviations of the adjusted copter position of up
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16 316 to 2 m without any external influence (Figure 6). Another test using a camera run in
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18 317 time-lapse mode observing a fixed position on the ground showed a slow but
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20 318 constant loss of height over time, that is only visible in time-lapse mode. For this two
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22 319 results even the 'fixed position' of the UAV cannot be treated as what the
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24 320 measurement principles consider to be a fixed position. This behavior was also
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26 321 observed with a second UAV (DJI Phantom 3 Professional).
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30 322 The critical on site distance for IR target detection is approximately 15 m. Further
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32 323 tests showed that the range could be extended to 20 to 25 m during night.
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34 324 The final results of the investigation were made between the post-processed tracks
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36 325 without (Table 2) and after Savitzky-Golay filtering (Table 3). Comparison of the time-
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38 326 averaged velocities in both the streamwise (U) and lateral (V) direction shows that
39
40 327 the filter had little effect on either of the mean estimates. The filter did however result
41
42 328 in a large reduction of the standard deviation in both the streamwise direction, with
43
44 329 an average reduction of 42% and lateral, with an average reduction of 44%. The
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46 330 reduction of the standard deviation by smoothing will also be investigated in future
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48 331 works comparing point velocity measurements to RAPTOR estimates, as it is
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50 332 expected to remove some noise from the post-processed data. The largest changes
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52 333 observed between the post-processed and smoothed data (Figure 7) were found in
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54 334 the maximum and minimum values, which is to be expected as one of the benefits of
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56 335 smoothing is to remove outliers from the data set. Here it was found that after
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3 336 smoothing, the maximum and minimum values were reduced on average by 29% in
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5 337 the streamwise direction, and 24% in the lateral.
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9 338 Discussion

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12 339 We presented a methodology capable of real-time estimation of water surface
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14 340 velocity. The system consisted of a UAV-mounted optical tracking module, which
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16 341 recorded the position of floating IR particles. In contrast to existing particle tracking
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18 342 methods, which rely heavily on image processing, the proposed system is capable of
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20 343 tracking the particle motion in real-time at up to 50 Hz, providing new capabilities for
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22 344 UAV-based velocimetry in rivers. The velocity was estimated for 12 unscaled tracks
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24 345 taken from two separate flights, before and after Savitzky-Golay filtering.
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28 346 Although only a limited number of flights at a single site were analyzed, preliminary
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30 347 results showed that the relatively high data recording rate of 50 Hz provides average
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32 348 sub-pixel deviations of particle position. A benefit of the high sampling rate, relative to
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34 349 the physical motion of the particles was that the applied filtering has little impact on
35
36 350 either the streamwise or lateral time-averaged velocities. However, as we are
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38 351 interested in robust real-time velocimetry, it is worth noting that the filter can lead to a
39
40 352 substantial (40% or more) reduction of the velocity estimate standard deviation. As
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42 353 expected, filtering the particle tracks also leads to a commensurate reduction in the
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44 354 velocity maxima.
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48 355 One source of error is the lateral motion of the UAV relative to the ground during
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50 356 flight. We found that the UAV had a mean deviation of around 2 m while hovering
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52 357 over a fixed position, which was substantially larger than the 0.8 m specified by the
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54 358 manufacturer (DJI, 2015). However, based on field experience this is well within the
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56 359 typical position accuracy of commodity GPS devices under standard field operating
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58 360 conditions.
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3 361 Similar to lateral drift, the constant loss of height was (during the short hovering time)
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5 362 within the manufacturer's data of a maximum deviation of 2.5 m in height (DJI, 2015).
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7 363 Accurate and robust height estimates are important as they impact the quality and
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9 364 accuracy of particle tracking position estimates. We used two different flight
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11 365 controllers (DJI NAZA-M V2 and embedded controller in the DJI Phantom 3
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13 366 professional for testing). Although we did not collect the necessary data to compare
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16 367 them directly, future research would benefit by observing and quantifying lateral and
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18 368 vertical drift under different conditions and with different drone manufacturers. This
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20 369 must be carried out to assess if the observed deviations are based on GPS system
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22 370 or on UAV hardware components and in-flight physics. Optical and radar positioning
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24 371 systems may be a solution as they can improve positioning accuracy at lower
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26 372 altitude. Another option is the use of a UAV with RTK-based GPS (Rieke et al.,
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28 373 2012). In the end, drift is unlikely to be completely eliminated and will require further
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30 374 devices and data processing methods to correct.
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33 375 We believe that the IR-emitting target and our preliminary field test results indicate
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35 376 that the methodology is proven suitable for further research. One disadvantage while
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37 377 using the current set-up is the use of offline filtering. Although this was not needed for
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39 378 real-time tracking, it was required to classify and correct spurious target object
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41 379 motion (e.g. recordings made after the particle had been removed from the water).
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43 380 This step could be removed in the future if the tracer particle floats are only activated
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45 381 upon contacting the water surface. This could be done with a hardware modification
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47 382 either manually or using a moisture switch.
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50 383 In addition to improving the particles, additional optimization could be carried out to
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52 384 improve the range. The current setup works up to a distance of ~15 m, tested for
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54 385 overcast ambient lighting. Weather conditions considering sunny days or rapid
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56 386 changes in lighting due to cloud cover warrant further field testing. If the range could
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3 387 be reliably increased for up to 100 m, a larger detection surface area could expand
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5 388 the use of the technology to large rivers and perhaps even limited coastal regions.
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7 389 Considering the nearly omnipresent risk of collision with surrounding vegetation near
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9 390 rivers, operating at higher altitudes can also help to remove some risk for field
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11 391 survey. The distance between IR target and sensor should therefore be increased to
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13 392 a minimum detection height of 20 to 25 m. This could be potentially done by
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15 393 increasing the number and luminosity of the IR emitters.
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17 394 An additional direction of optimization is the use of multiple reference targets in order
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19 395 to provide real-time scaling of the particle tracks. This would allow for true, scaled
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21 396 velocity estimation. This would significantly enhance the practical application of our
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23 397 method compared with existing methods which use collections of natural or artificial
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25 398 particles (Fujita et al., 2015; Patalano et al., 2015). We are also concerned with the
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27 399 loss of multiple IR particles in the river environment, which is likely to occur if tracking
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29 400 several particles in a large river. Methods to enhance the recovery of multiple IR
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31 401 targets, e.g. by spanning a net, will have to be considered and tested before large
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33 402 numbers of IR particles can be tested in the field.
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35 403 Finally, it should be mentioned that real-time particle tracking methods could make
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37 404 use of much more than just IR particles. An example are UAV-mounted thermal
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39 405 cameras, which are becoming available at lower cost, thus a possible solution would
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41 406 be to use thermal tracers (de Lima and Abrantes, 2014). If a reasonable method for
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43 407 tracer injection in field were to be established, the physical particles could be entirely
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45 408 replaced by heated water. Another option is to use floatable GPS devices (Stockdale
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47 409 et al., 2007), especially if the rivers are too large or have poor aerial line-of-sight.
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49 410 However, similar to our IR particles on Styrofoam floats, GPS devices do not solve
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51 411 the potential environmental risk associated with equipment loss in the river.
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412 Conclusions

413 The major contribution of our work is to illustrate that it is now possible to capture not
414 only the time-averaged velocity in rivers at a large scale, but the local motion of
415 surface particles in real-time. The long-term objective of our research is to capture
416 and classify large coherent structures in rivers. Time-averaged flow analyses smooth
417 out these flow features, however the data obtained by the proposed method may
418 provide a new way to capture large-scale, instationary regions of the velocity field
419 represented by persistent and chaotic regions of the flow field. The study of coherent
420 structures may provide new insights into the underlying physical mechanisms
421 between flow and transport. Indeed, recent advances in fundamental fluid mechanics
422 have motivated our research. We hope that the RAPTOR concept sparks interest in
423 the geomorphological community on the topic of coherent structures in rivers, which
424 have been shown to play a role in material transport processes at multiple scales, but
425 often remain neglected in most analyses due to the lack of suitable field
426 measurement methods.

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60**547 Figures**

548 Figure 1. Aerial image of the study site and its position at river Brigach, Black Forest,
549 Germany. The region of interest (ROI), in red, has 10 ground control points with 1 m
550 offset (top of ROI). The single ground control point at the bottom of the ROI is the
551 reference target. Flow direction is from left to right.

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553 Figure 2. Hardware. (a) CMUCam5 used for real-time particle tracking. The unit is
554 small and lightweight, making it ideal for UAV applications. (b) Custom made
555 hexacopter with 4,5 kW power, with a maximum payload of around 2.5 kg and a total
556 weight with this configuration of approximately 4.8 kg. The copter is controlled by DJI
557 NAZA-M V2 Multirotor Autopilot.

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559 Figure 3. Data processing workflow from initial raw data, to the final tracks after
560 undergoing data fusion.

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562 Figure 4. Data processing work flow. (a) Raw input data exported from CMUCam5.
563 (b) Track classification. (c) Position correction using the reference target (red point at
564 lower left). (d) Spurious track point filtering. (e) Dataset fusion.

565

566 Figure 5. All six tracks from flight 1, the point locations after completion of the post-
567 processing workflow (black), and the final tracks using the Savitzky-Golay filter (red).
568 Gaps between post-processed data filled by the smoothed data can be clearly seen.
569 The initial positions of the smoothed tracks in this figure were all set to coincide at
570 (0,0) for illustration purposes.

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3 572 Figure 6. Deviation of the Ground Control Point (GCP) from initial position (Euclidean
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5 573 distance in pixels) over time for the 2 studied datasets. First raise correspond to the
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7 574 elevation of UAV.
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11 576 Figure 7. Comparison of the filtered data versus the raw data.
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577 Tables

578 Table 1: Assessment of UAV self-motion during tracking.

Flight number	Track	Duration (s)	$\mu_{\Delta x}$ (px)	$\mu_{\Delta y}$ (xd)	$\sigma_{\Delta x}$ (px)	$\sigma_{\Delta y}$ (px)
1	1	3.52	0.07	0.12	0.55	0.53
1	2	4.21	-0.04	-0.04	0.53	0.60
1	3	4.09	0.01	0.00	0.41	0.43
1	4	3.49	0.02	-0.01	0.21	0.44
1	5	3.25	0.00	0.03	0.49	0.65
1	6	2.77	0.02	-0.01	0.39	0.55
2	1	4.13	-0.01	-0.01	0.34	0.49
2	2	2.98	0.05	-0.02	0.35	0.53
2	3	3.10	-0.02	0.10	0.43	0.60
2	4	3.45	0.03	0.03	0.43	0.56
2	5	3.82	-0.01	0.02	0.19	0.61
2	6	2.75	0.05	0.02	0.48	0.60

579

580 Table 2: Analysis of the unscaled velocity for the post-processed, unfiltered data. All
 581 values in [px/s].

Flight	Track	U	V	σ_U	σ_V	U _{min}	U _{max}	V _{min}	V _{max}
1	1	59.0	4.9	57.6	35.0	-47.6	500.0	-125.0	105.3
1	2	46.2	7.0	36.6	35.6	-50.0	150.0	-95.2	100.0
1	3	46.1	1.5	34.3	32.3	-52.6	157.9	-95.2	100.0
1	4	45.2	4.5	30.1	25.8	0.0	100.0	-66.7	95.2
1	5	58.2	1.8	51.5	35.5	-100.0	190.5	-95.2	111.1
1	6	68.8	14.3	36.7	34.3	-50.0	150.0	-50.0	105.3
2	1	47.1	20.4	41.3	36.4	-50.0	150.0	-52.6	142.9
2	2	43.5	20.8	42.2	30.6	-50.0	150.0	-50.0	111.1
2	3	43.6	20.2	17.5	14.1	-3.4	97.6	-10.7	52.6
2	4	62.1	-2.7	51.8	29.4	-58.8	238.1	-90.9	58.8
2	5	55.7	3.0	44.9	29.9	-50.0	150.0	-66.7	100.0
2	6	49.0	0.0	51.0	24.9	-95.2	157.9	-90.9	50.0

582

583 Table 3: Analysis of the unscaled velocity for the data after Savitzky-Golay filtering.

584 All values in [px/s].

Flight	Track	U	V	σ_U	σ_V	U _{min}	U _{max}	V _{min}	V _{max}
1	1	54.7	2.8	21.5	17.1	0.0	117.1	-52.6	59.1
1	2	46.1	7.3	19.2	13.1	-50.0	105.3	-50.0	52.6
1	3	46.0	1.7	20.3	17.2	0.0	157.9	-95.2	97.2
1	4	45.4	4.2	15.2	12.9	0.0	100.0	-47.6	50.0
1	5	58.1	1.5	39.5	19.4	-100.0	175.5	-50.0	52.6
1	6	70.0	14.4	23.0	22.7	0.0	150.0	-50.0	105.3
2	1	47.3	19.7	19.6	26.4	0.0	103.0	-47.6	97.2
2	2	43.6	20.2	17.5	14.1	-3.4	97.6	-10.7	52.6
2	3	65.8	13.2	33.5	17.5	-47.6	157.9	-16.9	95.2
2	4	64.3	-3.5	44.8	22.7	-45.5	334.6	-121.3	50.0
2	5	55.7	3.4	25.6	13.3	-50.0	150.0	-50.0	50.0
2	6	47.2	-1.0	30.9	15.6	-190.8	150.0	-75.8	50.0

585

All six tracks from flight 1, the point locations after completion of the post-processing workflow (black), and the final tracks using the Savitzky-Golay filter (red). Gaps between post-processed data filled by the smoothed data can be clearly seen. The initial positions of the smoothed tracks in this figure were all set to coincide at (0,0) for illustration purposes.

185x139mm (274 x 274 DPI)

